

Climate Risks to Offshore Oil and Gas Structures in Ghana's Tano Cape Three Points Basin

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Executive Summary

This study presents a preliminary assessment of climate-related risks to offshore infrastructure in Ghana's Tano Cape Three Points Basin, focusing on the potential impacts of sea-level rise on Floating Production, Storage and Offloading (FPSO) units and nearby coastal communities. Using global datasets and open-source climate risk tools, the results show that projected sea-level increases, particularly under high-emission scenarios, could significantly heighten the exposure of offshore assets and low-lying urban areas such as Accra and Takoradi to coastal flooding. These findings point to the urgent need to integrate climate risk considerations into infrastructure planning and resilience strategies.

The study recommends initiating climate risk audits for offshore energy infrastructure, incorporating future climate projections into design and maintenance standards, and enhancing early warning systems for coastal settlements. Nature-based solutions like mangrove restoration should be explored to provide protective buffers along the coast, while institutional capacity must be strengthened to develop and apply integrated risk models tailored to local conditions. Although technical and contextual limitations exist, this initial work lays a solid foundation for advancing climate resilience planning and informs future research and policy discussions aimed at safeguarding Ghana's offshore energy sector in the face of escalating climate threats.

1. Introduction

Infrastructure systems worldwide face growing risks from climate change, with hazards such as flooding, cyclones, heatwaves, sea-level rise, and droughts threatening the reliability and safety of roads, railways, ports, energy grids, water supply, and telecommunications (Leal Filho et al., 2024; Verschuur et al., 2024). Developing countries and coastal megacities are particularly vulnerable due to limited adaptive capacity, older infrastructure, and rapid urbanization, while low-income communities often suffer most from disruptions due to their reliance on vulnerable systems. Climate risks to infrastructure are measured using integrated frameworks that combine analysis of climate hazards (such as floods, heatwaves, and storms), assessment of asset vulnerability and fragility, and mapping of exposure across networks and sectors (Dawson et al., 2018a, 2018b).

Africa faces severe climate risks to its infrastructure, with 70% of cities confronting floods, extreme heat, and mudslides, while 70% of infrastructure expected by 2070 remains unbuilt, offering a critical opportunity to integrate climate resilience (Africa Development Bank, 2024; World Bank Group, 2025). Without urgent action, climate impacts could erase 2–4% of Africa's GDP annually by 2040, with loss and damage costs projected at \$290–440 billion, underscoring the need for upgraded engineering standards, private-sector investment, and integrated green-gray infrastructure (United Nations, 2023; World Bank Group, 2025).

Offshore infrastructure globally faces escalating climate risks, with the frequency of climate-related natural disasters nearly tripling over the past three decades and physical damage from extreme weather—such as hurricanes, floods, and heatwaves—now a leading cause of disruptions and insured losses in the sector (Allianz, 2025; Marsh & McLennan, 2024). Ghana has made approximately 30 offshore oil and gas discoveries, with three fields currently in production. Beyond hydrocarbons, the country's offshore waters support vital

economic activities such as fishing. Given these developments, it is crucial to assess the risks posed by climate-related hazards such as extreme storms, sea-level rise, and coastal flooding to offshore infrastructure and coastal communities. The overall goal of the project is to assess the risk of climate change to offshore infrastructure, particularly Floating Production, Storage and Offloading (FPSO) units in Ghana’s Tano Cape Three Points Basin using appropriate climate and engineering modelling tools. The specific objectives of the project include:

1. To identify and analyse key climate-related hazards (e.g., sea-level rise, storm surges, extreme wave and wind events) likely to affect FPSOs in the Tano Cape Three Points Basin.
2. To evaluate the structural and operational vulnerabilities of FPSOs to projected climate hazards using engineering and probabilistic risk assessment models.
3. To develop a climate risk profile for offshore infrastructure in the basin, providing recommendations for adaptation, resilience planning, and future policy formulation

2. Methodology

The project followed a five-step methodology, as illustrated in the flowchart in Figure 1. The specific tasks to be undertaken under each step are outlined below.

Figure 1. Summary of the methodology

- **Data Collection & Preparation:** All the foundational data required for risk and vulnerability modelling will be collected. The first task is to collect both historical and projected climate hazard data relevant to offshore environments, including sea-level rise, storm surges, and wind speed trends under various climate scenarios.
- **Hazard, Exposure & Vulnerability Analysis:** Building on the prepared data, this phase focuses on modelling the exposure and vulnerability of offshore infrastructure to climate hazards. Hazard maps will be overlaid with the spatial

locations of infrastructure assets to assess exposure levels across different hazard types and intensities.

- **Criticality & Cascading Impact Assessment:** The project will then evaluate the relative importance of each infrastructure asset and its potential to cause broader system disruptions.
- **Adaptation Modelling & Evaluation:** With risks and critical vulnerabilities identified, this phase will focus on designing and evaluating adaptation options.
- **Policy Recommendations & Dissemination:** The final phase of the project will focus on translating research findings into actionable policy guidance and stakeholder engagement.

3. Results

A dataset has been compiled on Ghana’s three operational FPSOs—FPSO Kwame Nkrumah, FPSO Prof. John Evans Atta Mills, and FPSO John Agyekum Kufuor (

Table 1). The dataset includes key technical and operational parameters essential for modelling climate-related risks to these offshore structures. These parameters will serve as foundational inputs for exposure, vulnerability, and risk assessment.

Table 1. Dataset gathered on Ghana’s three FPSOs

Parameter	FPSO Kwame Nkrumah (SOFEC, 2025; Tullow Oil, 2022, 2021)	FPSO John Evans Atta Mills(MODEC, 2025; Tullow, 2015; Tullow Oil, 2022)	FPSO John Agyekum Kufuor(Offshore Energy, 2017)
Field/Block	Jubilee Field	TEN (Tweneboa, Enyenra, Ntomme) Fields	OCTP (Offshore Cape Three Points) Block
Operator/Client	Tullow Ghana Ltd.	Tullow Ghana Ltd.	ENI Ghana/Vitol/GNPC
First Oil/Operation	Dec 2010	Aug 2016	2017
Water Depth	1,320 m	1,500 m	1,000 m (avg)
Hull/Conversion	Converted VLCC	Converted VLCC (Centennial J)	Newbuild by Keppel Shipyard, Singapore
Storage Capacity	1,600,000 barrels	1,700,000 barrels	1,400,000–1,700,000 barrels
Oil Production	120,000 bopd	80,000 bopd	58,000 bopd
Gas Production/Handling	160 MMscfd gas produced	180 MMscfd gas produced	150 MMscfd gas injection; 210 MMscfd export
Water Injection	232,000 bwpd	(Data not specified)	(Data not specified)
Mooring System	SOFEC External Turret	SOFEC External Turret	Turret mooring (details not specified)
Dimensions	Length: 272,000 dwt; 358.6 m x 59 m x 19.6 m	Length: 340 m	Length: 333 m; Beam: 60 m
Design Life	20 years	20 years	20 years (without dry docking)
Climate Risk Factors	Exposure to sea-level rise, increased storm intensity, corrosion, heatwaves	Similar exposure: deepwater design may offer resilience	Similar exposure: double hull and newbuild features for resilience

International Standards and Frameworks

Table 2 presents some international standards and frameworks commonly used to assess climate risks for FPSOs. These have been identified through a review of relevant literature, industry guidelines, and global best practices in offshore infrastructure risk management:

Table 2. Review of some applicable international standards and frameworks

Standard/Framework	Scope	Climate Risk Elements	Applicability
ISO Management System Standards (Amended 2024)	Requires organizations to integrate climate change risks into contextual analysis and management systems.	All climate-related hazards (e.g., sea-level rise, storms, heatwaves) as part of organizational risk assessments.	Mandates climate risk evaluation in FPSO design, operations, and maintenance.
API RP 75W (2024)	Safety and Environmental Management System for Offshore Wind (adaptable to FPSOs).	Risk assessment for extreme weather, wave height, wind directionality, and sea-level rise.	Provides framework for systematic review of climate risks in offshore operations.
IOGP Report 377 (2006)	Guidelines for managing marine risks associated with FPSOs.	Metocean conditions (waves, currents, wind), collision risks, and hydrocarbon handling.	Addresses design and operational risks from climate-related hazards like storms and waves.
DNV-ST-0116 (2023)	Floating offshore wind turbine structures (adaptable to FPSOs).	Fatigue from wave action, corrosion due to saltwater intrusion, and extreme weather loads.	Guides resilient design against climate stressors.
DNV-ST-0119 (2023)	Climate change resilience for offshore structures.	Sea-level rise, storm intensity, temperature extremes, and corrosion acceleration.	Provides quantitative methods for climate risk modelling in FPSO lifecycle assessments.
TCFD/ESRS E1 Framework	Task Force on Climate-related Financial Disclosures and EU Sustainability Reporting Standards.	28 climate hazards (e.g., flooding, heatwaves, cyclones) and financial impacts.	Used by operators like SBM Offshore to assess physical and transitional risks for FPSOs.
IPCC CMIP6 Database	Climate model projections for scenario analysis (RCP 2.6, 8.5).	Sea-level rise, storm surges, temperature extremes, and wind/wave patterns.	Basis for future climate risk modelling in FPSO mooring, hull design, and operations.
BSEE/API RP 75	Safety and Environmental Management Systems (SEMS) for offshore operations.	Extreme weather preparedness, asset integrity under climate stressors.	Aligns with API RP 75W for offshore wind/FPSO risk management.

Using the NASA Sea Level Projection Tool and Climate Central’s Sea Level Rise and Coastal Risk Maps, I conducted an initial assessment of projected sea-level changes around the Cape Three Points area offshore Ghana (Felikson et al., 2022; Gornitz and Kanciruk, 1989). Based on two scenarios, Figure 2 illustrates the potential for significant sea-level rise in the coming decades. Figure 3 highlights the relationship between global

temperature increases and sea-level changes in the region. The results suggest that exceeding the Paris Agreement target of 1.5°C above pre-industrial levels could lead to substantially higher sea-level rise and exacerbate climate-related risks to offshore infrastructure in the Cape Three Points area.

Figure 2. Two scenarios of sea level change profile of Ghana's Tano Cape Three Point Basin

Figure 3. Effect of Temperature change on sea level change profile of Ghana's Tano Cape Three Point Basin

To better understand the potential local impacts of the projected sea-level rise, I evaluated its implications for coastal flooding in Ghana focusing particularly on the cities of Accra and Takoradi, which are both economically and strategically significant. Using flood risk projection tools and sea-level rise data up to the year 2060, I assessed how rising seas could affect low-lying coastal zones. *Figure 4* illustrates the areas at heightened risk of coastal flooding, with the brown-shaded regions on the map indicating zones of potential inundation. The results suggest that not only Accra and Takoradi but also several other settlements along Ghana's coastline could become increasingly vulnerable to flooding if sea levels continue to rise under current or high-emission scenarios. This has important implications for infrastructure planning, urban development, and the resilience of coastal communities.

Figure 4. Impact of sea level rise on coastal flooding.

5. Discussion

The results from this preliminary assessment show the growing vulnerability of offshore oil and gas infrastructure in Ghana's Tano Cape Three Points Basin to sea-level rise driven by global temperature increases. Projections from the NASA Sea Level Projection Tool and Climate Central's Coastal Risk Maps reveal that if global warming exceeds the 1.5°C target of the Paris Agreement, the region could face substantially higher sea levels, increasing the likelihood of climate-related disruptions to critical infrastructure such as FPSO units. This highlights the need for Ghana to prioritize climate resilience in its offshore energy sector by integrating advanced monitoring technologies, re-evaluating design parameters for offshore platforms, and promoting nature-based coastal defences like mangrove restoration to reduce shoreline erosion. At the policy level, these findings suggest the need to mainstream climate risk assessments into national energy planning, coastal zoning regulations, and infrastructure investment frameworks to ensure long-term operational stability and energy security.

Despite these valuable insights, the study has some limitations. The modelling tools used are global-scale platforms that, while robust, may lack the spatial resolution and contextual specificity needed for highly localized risk assessments. In addition, technical constraints, particularly in adapting complex codes from the NISMOC-CR framework limited the integration of a full multi-sectoral systems analysis in this preliminary phase. Future research should focus on developing or customizing high-resolution, Ghana-specific models that combine sea-level projections with local topographic, hydrological, and socio-economic data to support more accurate vulnerability mapping. Investigating the potential for hybrid adaptation solutions and assessing their cost-effectiveness and feasibility in the Ghanaian context would be critical. Implementation challenges such as limited technical capacity, financing constraints, and regulatory bottlenecks should also be systematically explored to ensure proposed interventions are realistic and scalable.

7. Conclusion

This report presents a preliminary assessment of climate-related risks to offshore oil and gas infrastructure in Ghana's Tano Cape Three Points Basin, with a focus on projected sea-level rise and its implications for infrastructure vulnerability and coastal flooding. By leveraging global climate data and open-source tools, the study highlights the growing risks to critical assets such as FPSO units, as well as the vulnerability of coastal cities.

While there are still technical challenges particularly in adapting and modifying existing models to fit the specific context of Ghana, the insights gained thus far provide a strong foundation for advancing the work. As I continue to refine the modelling, this initial study serves as a crucial step toward developing an integrated climate risk profile and resilience strategy for Ghana's offshore energy sector. The lessons from the Summer School will continue to inform the next phases of the project and guide the training of students in this emerging field of climate resilience.

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